

Tourist's Behaviour: A Case Study of Mysuru City

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Abstract

Tourist's behaviour is one important study in the field of tourism geography as it influence on the expenditure pattern of the tourist's at the place of destination. It is adapt of the tourist's to the specific situation or a product. The main objective of this study is to know the behaviour of the tourist's of the Mysuru city. It is the most important indicator or predictor of future development of tourism in Mysuru city.

Keywords: Tourists, Tourism, Behaviour, Mysuru, Domestic, International.

Introduction

The behaviour of the tourist refers to the way in which tourists behave according to their attitudes before, during and after travelling. It is adapt to the specific situation or a product. Knowledge regarding travel behavior will help in the overall development of tourism, marketing and product planning for example tourism products such as tourist spots, resorts, hotels, shopping etc. Tourist behavior starts in the planning and implementation stages of the holidays. The behavior of tourist's is the most important indicator or predictor of future development of tourism. It is important to know the knowledge of tourist and his association with destination selection. It plays a critical role in predicting future travel patterns of the tourists. Erasmus et.al. (2001) considers that it is necessary for the study of consumer behavior to adopt to the specific situations for products that subject of purchase. Individual decisions in the decision making process can be more or less risky, depending on the final product. Their model of consumer behaviour also includes all the steps that occur well before the purchase and afterwards. Peter and Olson (2002) propose a model for consumer behavior in which they include the importance of information. They summaries consumer behaviour as a cognitive process. Through this process the consumer normally decides how to solve their problems. Pearce (2005) states that knowing the behaviour of the tourist has practical value for all tourism stakeholders. Li et al. (2013) examined the effect of belonging to a certain generation on tourists and found that different generations possess different histories of destination visits, exhibit different wishes and preferences for the future, and also follow different criteria for the assessment of tourist destinations. They also partially confirmed the claim that different generations use different

sources of information, and that they have different preferences for activities during the trip. Scott et al. (2014) states that few recent studies have discussed whether it was even viable to use classical marketing concepts for the study of tourist behaviour, since this may cast doubt on the validity and the possibility of application of the models for tourism.

Objective

The main objective of the study is to study the behaviour of the tourist of Mysuru city.

Methodology

A simple hundred questionnaire is served kept in mind of the age group and Sex for both domestic and international tourist at Mysuru Palace ground. The answered obtained is converted in to percentage and the same has been presented in the farm of table and charts.

Factors influencing on the behavior of the tourist

The tourist behavior changes from individual to individual, place to place and it also influence on the others. Behavior of an individual tourist can also be an indicator of the behavior of others. The behavior of the tourist influenced by the following factors

Social Norms

Tourist behaviour at the home town and at the place of destination and with the others at both the places reflected by his social status. The social norms include position of the tourists and his family in the society influences on the behavior of the tourists. If a tourist has earned a good status in the society certainly it influences on the selection of the tourists places, mode of travel selection of t stay and his expenditure pattern.

Cultural Values

The cultural values of the tourist is an important factor which influences on th behavior of the tourist. Attitude and habits of the tourist are important indicator of the cultural values. The good habits and attitude of the tourists influences on the place of destination and his social relation at the place of destination. The good attitude of the tourists and his family will help in keeping the place of destination in clean manner. Now a day's most of the tourist's spots are suffering from the solid waste management because of the lack of attitude of the tourist towards the place of destination.

Personal Factors

Such as gender, lifestyle, education, age and number of family members etc. influences on the bheaviour of the tourists especially in the initial stages of the tourism that is selection and planning

of place of destination. The length of stay, mode of transportation, selection of boarding and lodging will be influenced by his personal factors.

Psychological Factors

Skills, perception and experience of the tourists is reflected by the behavior of the tourists. The planning, selection of place of destination, mode of transportation, planning of stay, time spend at the places of visit at destination will be governed by the skill perception and experience of the tourist.

Motivation

It is a strong factor behind the tourism the plan for the tourism by a tourist always induced by motivation. The motivation either by friends or by family members and some time the pull factors of the place of destination and push factor at the place of stay of a tourist also be a factors of motivation for example the hot summer at the place of stay will be a push factor where as the cool weather at the place of destination is a factor of pull, the best example for this is Ooty.. The motivation not only influences on the initial stage of planning for tourism it also strongly influences on the expenditure pattern of the tourist.

Location of the Tourist

Location, topography and weather are the important factors which influence on the behavior of the tourist and act as a push factors. The tourists who reside at costal areas would like to visit the mountains areas and vice-versa. Like wise the people of hot weather wish to go to cool temperate placers.

Weather also an important factor which influence on the behavior of the tourists. The people of tropical regions are short tempered, where as the people of temperate region are cool and mild.

Destination

The destination of tourist place act as pull factor which influence on he behavior of the tourist. It includes historical places like Mysore, costal areas, beeches, waterfall, hill stations wild life sanctuary etc. these places attracts the tourist. The tourists according to their choice and interest visit the places

The economic condition of the tourist- Purchasing power and price are the two important factors which influence on the behavior. The selection of place, mode of transportation, choice of boarding and lodging, length of stay and purchase of things of interest all are influenced by the economic condition of the tourist.

Tourist Visit

The behavior of the tourist varies according to his companion and it also influence on the choice selection of place and entire tour programme. His behavior varies depending on situation, whether he visits alone, with family, friends or with colleagues.

Demography Influence on the Purpose of Visit

Every tourist and tourism has some definite activates and result in the form of outcome. The outcome is satisfaction, and enjoyment.

In the study area eight main activities are listed by getting the opinion of the tourist and are shown in the following table which is graphically represented in the form of pie-chart. This explains the behavior or the interest of the tourist both domestic and international.

From the above figure it is clear that recreation and water sports is the main interested activity of the tourist's followed by visiting Zoo and Palace. Dining (13.4), touring the country side (10.7), visiting cultural heritage place (13.86), recreational site and water sports (17.2), Zoo (14.6) followed by shopping (10.46), visiting a religious place (9.92) and sightseeing (9.8).

Dining at Restaurants

Dining is a main activity of the tourism. Eating the special items of the local place attracts the tourist. Mysuru known for Mysuru Masaladosa and Mysurr-pak naturally attracts all category of the tourist. 15.2% of male and children of the domestic tourists and male and female of the international tourists considered it as one of the important purpose of tourism, surprisingly female domestic tourists (5.2%) are not considered it as their main purpose of visit.

Shopping

This is one of the main important activities of female and children of the domestic tourist but not for the international tourist. Mysuru is famous for Mysore silk, wood carving and toys. 19.5% of the children and 16, 5% of the female of the domestic tourist's purpose of visit is for shopping.

Visiting Religious Site

The behavior of the tourist decides the type of tourism and place of destination. The behavior of the children and the male of international tourist widely differs. 6.7% of the children and 2.5% of the male international tourist's wish to visit the religious place Chamundi hill but the highest of 18.8% of the female domestic tourist's main activity of tourism is to visit Chamundi hill

Table 4.4 Demography influence on the purpose of visit

Activity	Things of Interest in (%)					
	Domestic			International		Total
	Male	Female	Children	Male	Female	
Dining at restaurants	15.2	5.2	15.2	16.2	15.2	13.4
Shopping	5.5	16.5	19.5	5.3	5.5	10.46
Visiting a Religious site	10.8	18.8	6.7	2.5	10.8	9.92
Sightseeing in a city	11	9	9	9	11	9.8

Touring the country side	11.3	7.3	9.3	14.3	11.3	10.7
Visiting a cultural heritage site	14.4	14.7	9.1	16.7	14.4	13.86
Visiting a recreational site & participating in water sports	17.3	15	16.7	19.7	17.3	17.2
Visiting Zoo	14.5	13.5	14.5	16.3	14.5	14.66

Source: personnel survey.

Sightseeing in a city

This is not widely attracted activity of the tourist. All category of the tourist to Mysuru are not showing interest in roam the city. Only 11% of domestic male and international female tourist and 9% of the female, children and male international are showing interest in this activity.

Touring country side

International tourists especially the male 14.3% are much attracted in traveling country side where as it is around 11.3% among the female. 11.3% of male and 9.3% of female of domestic tourists are also interested in traveling country side. This activity is not much attracted among the children.

Figure-4.7

Visiting cultural heritage site

Mysuru known for world famous palace and St. Philomena's Church are the important heritage site at the Mysuru which attracts 16.7% of the male and 14.4% of female international tourists. Around 14.4% domestic tourists and less percentage of children are interested in visiting heritage sites.

Visiting Recreational Site & Participating in Water Sports

This is the activity which attracts all kinds of tourists especially in the summer vacation. Karnji lake and G.R.S. Fantasy Park and Varuna lake are the main attraction of Mysuru. Highest percentage of 17.3% male domestic tourists and highest percentage of international tourist's male 19.7% and female 17.3% main activity of tourism is to visit these places whereas 15% of children and 16.7% of female domestic tourist are attracted towards this activity.

Visiting Zoo

All the categories of the tourist are showing same kind of interest. 13.5% of the children and 14.5% of male and 13.5% of female domestic tourist's activity is to visit Zo where as 16.3%. Male and 14.5% female international tourists are also attracted towards this activity.

Findings of the Study

1. The behavior of the tourist's depends on the age, sex, and category of the tourists.
2. It influence on the activity of the tourists. Especially on the Selection place and expenditure of the torusits
3. Tourists in the Mysore are more interested in visiting recreational place and Water sports at G.R.S Fantasy Park and Varuna lake.
4. Visiting Zoo and Palace are the next option of the tourists.
5. Female and children of domestic tourist's are more interested in shopping than the the international tourists.

Impact of Tourists behavior

The behavior and perception of the tourists has several impacts on the place of tourism and are listed as follows

1. Planning for tourism
2. Expenditure pattern
3. Choice of tourism places
4. Mode of travel
5. Type of selection of Boarding and lodging
6. Length of stay

Conclusion

The age sex and category of the tourist are the main factors influencing on the behavior of the tourist. The behavior of the tourist in turn influence on the planning and development of tourism as the behavior of the tourist influencing on the plan for tourism and type of tourism which can be very well noticed from the above study. This study will help especially on the expenditure pattern of the tourist which going to study in the next chapter.

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